

PRESENT VALUE MODEL BETWEEN PRICES AND DIVIDENDS IN THE BRAZILIAN STOCK MARKET: FIRM-LEVEL EVIDENCE FROM PANEL TECHNIQUES APPLIED TO NONSTATIONARY AND POTENTIALLY COINTEGRATED PROCESSES

Rivera Rivera, Edward
 Marçal, Emerson
 Martin, Diogenes Leiva

ABSTRACT

The Present Value Model (PVM) – in which current security prices depend upon the present value of future discounted dividends, where the discount rate is equivalent to the required rate of return – is one of the long-standing principles of Finance Theory. This relationship has gathered attention from empirical literature due to the rapid price increase in stock markets throughout the decade of 1990 and its subsequent decline. The objective of this work is to analyze the validity of the PVM between prices and dividends at the firm level from panel techniques applied to nonstationary and potentially cointegrated processes for the Brazilian stock market. Results indicate that, in the Present Value Model with Constant Expected Returns, the hypothesis that real prices and real dividends have a unit root cannot be rejected. Respective panel cointegration tests indicate that real prices and real dividends are cointegrated, and hence attributing validity to the PVM under the hypothesis of constant expected returns. Regarding the Present Value Model with Time-Varying Expected Returns, the hypothesis that real log prices and real log dividends are nonstationary $I(1)$ and that log price-dividend ratio is $I(0)$ cannot be rejected as analyzed in theory for the validation of the underlying model. The respective panel cointegration tests yield evidence that the real log prices and real log dividends series are cointegrated, validating the PVM under the hypothesis of time-varying expected returns. Considering FMOLS and DOLS estimators for panel cointegration models, results indicate that stock prices are overvalued under either constant or time-varying expected returns.

Keywords: Present Value Model; Unit Root; Cointegration; Time-Series; Nonstationary Panels.

JEL: C10 G10 G14

1. INTRODUCTION

The Present Value Model (PVM) or Rational Valuation Formula (RVF) – concept in which current security prices depend upon the present value of discounted future dividends, where the discount rate is equivalent to the required rate of return – is one of the fundamental principles of Finance Theory. This model has gathered renewed attention in empirical literature, whose interest arises from the rapid stock price increase in the 1990s and its subsequent fall. As stock prices rose, analysts questioned whether the fundamental value of a stock was linked to innovations in dividends and interest rates, since low dividends payouts and record-high stock prices suggested stock price overvaluation.

Previous empirical analysis of the PVM and of the long-run relationship between prices and dividends is predominantly based upon two cointegration approaches. First, as Campbell and Shiller (1987) observe, real prices and real dividends should cointegrate, i.e. exhibit a stable long-run relationship. In this case, the cointegrating parameter provides an estimate of the inverse discount rate. Second, as in Campbell and Shiller (1988a,b), allowing for a time-varying discount rate, the difference between log dividends and log prices must exhibit $I(0)$ stationarity.

However, empirical evidence is mixed. Specifically, in the original paper by Campbell and Shiller (1987), as well as further work based on similar methodology such as Diba and Grossman (1988), Brooks and Katsaris (2003), Kapetanios, Shin and Snell (2006), the results from cointegration tests between prices and dividends are ambiguous. Similarly, empirical evidence that provide support for the PVM from tests for $I(0)$ stationarity of the log price-dividend ratio is relatively scarce, and several studies report evidence of $I(1)$ non-stationarity as observed in Froot and Obstfeld (1991), Lamont (1998), Balke and Wohar (2002).

Cohen, Polk and Vuolteenaho (2001), Vuolteenaho (2002) and Jung and Shiller (2005) suggest a greater likelihood for the PVM to be validated at the firm level rather than at the aggregate level (stock market index). As Jung and Shiller (2005) analyze, although information about cash flows and future prospects of individual companies are well understood by investors, the same degree of clarity may not apply to the market with respect to changes in the pattern of aggregate dividends or earnings flow in a country's stock market.

Among recent works examining the validity of the PVM at the aggregate stock market index level are those of Campbell and Shiller (1987), Campbell and Shiller (1988a,b), Fama and French (1988), Cecchetti, Lam and Mark (1990), Timmermann (1995), Kim, Morley and Nelson (2001), Dupuis and Tessier (2003), Manzan (2004), Su, Chang and Chen (2007). Some Brazilian stock market empirical findings applying similar methodology as Campbell e Shiller (1987, 1988a,b) were obtained by Anchite and Issler (2001) and Morales (2006). Considering these latter authors, whereas the PVM with time-varying returns is not statistically rejected, evidence points either towards a rejection or failure to reject the model, though with weaker statistical significance.

Concerning the few empirical works testing the validity of the PVM at the firm level, Nasseh and Strauss (2004), Goddard, McMillan and Wilson (2008) employ U.S. and U.K. data, respectively, in order to assess the underlying model under time-varying returns, and point out that panel methods are particularly useful when the available time period is relatively short, providing a gain in power precision and avoiding structural shifts in the data that occur over longer time periods. These authors found that the examination of the rational valuation formula at the firm level appears to be somewhat more supportive of the present value model than previous studies based on aggregated stock price and dividend index data.

Thus, the following research question is posed in this paper: In Brazil, is there a stable long-run relationship between the present value of an asset (real prices) and its respective discounted earnings (real dividends), at the microeconomic level (firm level), in order to

validate the Present Value Model and, therefore, expectations and rationality of economic agents in the financial market, through first generation unit root and cointegration tests as well as dynamic panel techniques?

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, the Present Value Model is briefly discussed. Section 3 provides technical details of the panel unit roots and cointegration tests adopted. Section 4 reports and interprets the results of these tests. Section 5 summarizes and concludes.

2. THE PRESENT VALUE MODEL

Campbell and Shiller (1987) observe that present value models are among the simplest dynamic stochastic models in economics. A present value model for two variables, y_t and Y_t (in this case, denoting stock price and dividend, respectively) imply that Y_t is a linear function of the discounted present value of expected future y_t :

$$Y_t = \theta(1 - \delta) \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \delta^i E_t y_{t+i} + c \quad (1)$$

where c , the constant, θ , the proportionality coefficient, and δ , the discount factor, are parameters that can be known a priori or may need to be estimated. E_t represents mathematical expectation, conditional on the full public information set I_t , which includes y_t and Y_t and in general exceeds the information set H_t available to the econometrician.

Despite the simplicity of the structure, there is a high degree of controversy concerning the validity of present value models for bonds, stocks and other economic variables. Testing the underlying equation holds the following implications: first, it is not clear how different statistical approaches (single-equation regression tests, cross-equation restrictions on a vector autoregression, variance bounds tests) are related to one another; second, statistical rejections of the model may not have much economic significance, since it may be rejected at the 5% level, even though it explains most of the variation in Y_t ; finally, variables y_t and Y_t usually require some transformation before the theory of stationary stochastic processes can be applied, but removal of deterministic linear trend may bias test procedures against the model if in fact y_t and Y_t are nonstationary in levels.

2.1 Present Value Model: Constant Expected Returns

Expected return is defined as:

$$E_t[R_{t+1}] = R \quad (2)$$

Return expectation in $t + 1$ as a function of price at the end of the period, with the addition of distributed dividends, is denoted as:

$$R = E_t[R_{t+1}] = \frac{E_t(P_{t+1} - P_t) + D_{t+1}}{P_t} \quad (3)$$

Actual price related to the expectation of future price and future dividends flow is represented as:

$$P_t = E_t \left[\frac{P_{t+1} + D_{t+1}}{1+R} \right] \quad (4)$$

This expectational difference equation can be solved forward K periods:

$$P_t = E_t \left[\sum_{i=1}^K \left(\frac{1}{1+R} \right)^i D_{t+i} \right] + E_t \left[\left(\frac{1}{1+R} \right)^K P_{t+K} \right] \quad (5)$$

As $K \rightarrow \infty$ (perpetuity investment), the second term $\rightarrow 0$. The equation of P_t for infinite periods is represented as:

$$P_t = E_t \left[\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{1+R} \right)^i D_{t+i} \right] \quad (6)$$

For the application of the time series theory, the equation is transformed into a relationship of stationary variables by subtracting a multiple of D_t on both sides of the equation:

$$P_t - \frac{D_t}{R} = \left(\frac{1}{R}\right) E_t \left[\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{1+R}\right)^i \Delta D_{t+1+i} \right] \quad (7)$$

On the left side, it is observed a stationary linear relationship (cointegration) between two nonstationary variables. The statement is true if the variation in dividends is stationary.

2.2 Present Value Model: Time-Varying Expected Returns

The loglinear approximation begins with the definition of the log return h_{t+1} of a stock:

$$h_{t+1} \equiv \log(P_{t+1} + D_{t+1}) - \log(P_t) \quad (8)$$

$$= p_{t+1} - p_t + \log(1 + \exp(d_{t+1} - p_{t+1})) \quad (9)$$

The last term on the right side of the equation is a nonlinear function of the log dividend-price ratio, $f(d_{t+1} - p_{t+1})$. As any nonlinear function, $f(x_{t+1})$ can be approximated around the mean of x_{t+1} , \bar{x} , through a first order Taylor expansion, $f(x_{t+1}) \approx f(\bar{x})(x_{t+1} - \bar{x})$, then:

$$h_{t+1} \approx \xi_{t+1} = k = \rho p_{t+1} + (1 - \rho)d_{t+1} - p_t \quad (10)$$

where k and p are linearization parameters: $k = -\ln(\rho) + (1 - \rho) \ln(\rho - 1)$ and $\rho = 1/[\exp(\bar{d} - \bar{p})]$.

Solving forward and establishing a condition relating to the inexistence of bubbles, $\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \rho^j p_{t+j} = 0$, hence:

$$p_t = \frac{k}{1-\rho} + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \rho^j [(1 - \rho)d_{t+1+j} - h_{t+1+j}] \quad (11)$$

The terminal condition excludes rational bubbles that would lead the log price of a stock to grow exponentially forever at a rate $1/\rho$ or faster.

The preceding equation relates two nonstationary processes with unit roots, the (log) stock price and its respective dividend d_{t+1+j} . For the application of the time series theory, it is possible to rewrite the preceding equation in terms of stationary series:

$$d_t - p_t = -\frac{k}{1-\rho} + E_t \left[\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \rho^j [-\Delta d_{t+1+j} + h_{t+1+j}] \right] \quad (12)$$

The log price-dividend ratio is $I(0)$ stationary, given that changes in dividends and in the discount rate are $I(0)$ stationary. By implication, log prices and log dividends are cointegrated, with a cointegration vector $[1, -1]$. Hence, empirical verification of this equation requires only the test for the $I(0)$ stationarity of the log price-dividend ratio and does not require the estimation of the (unknown) cointegration parameter.

3. ECONOMETRIC PROCEDURES

Panel data studies, until very recently, have ignored the crucial stationarity (ADF and Phillips-Perron) and cointegration (Engle-Granger and Johansen) tests. Nevertheless, with the growing involvement of macroeconomic applications in the panel data tradition, whose focus has shifted towards examining the asymptotics of macro panels with large T (length of the time series) and N (number of cross-sections), the issues of stationarity and cointegration have recently emerged in panel data as well. Although the literature on time series studies successfully answers stationary issues, the adoption of similar tests on panel data is yet in progress. The major differences between time-series and panel unit root and cointegration tests can be summarized as follows:

- a. Panel data allows the observation of patterns and relationships in the data that may not be detectable at the stock market aggregate level due to data smoothing caused by aggregation.
- b. Panel data methods can test various approaches considering different degrees of heterogeneity among individuals.
- c. In panel data analysis, so far, one cannot be sure as to the validity of rejecting a unit root.
- d. The power of panel unit root tests increases as N increases. This power increase is much more robust than in the size of the one observed in the standard low-power DF and ADF tests applied to small samples.
- e. The additional cross-sectional components incorporated in panel data models provide better properties of panel unit root tests, compared with the low-power standard ADF for time series samples.
- f. Panel cointegration tests, in comparison to individual time series tests, have increased power especially for small T , which is common in the cases data is limited to the post war period.

Testing for unit roots in panels is not a common practice as it is testing for unit roots in time series studies. The statistical methods applied in this paper relate to the works by Levin and Lin (1993), Levin, Lin and Chu (2002), Im, Pesaran and Shin (2003), Breitung (2000) and Hadri (2000). Recent panel cointegration tests applied are those developed by Kao (1999), Pedroni (1997, 1999, 2000, 2004) and Maddala and Wu (1999).

In addition, between-dimension FMOLS (Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares) and DOLS (Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares) estimators from Pedroni (1996, 2000, 2001) are applied, since the asymptotic properties of the estimators of the regression coefficients and the associated statistical tests for panel cointegrated regression models are different from those of the time series cointegration regression models.

4. RESULTS

In order to assess the present value model at the firm level for the Brazilian stock market, datasets on prices and dividends have been used at an annual frequency for the period of January 1987 to December 2008. The initial period is based on the availability of data platform, considering that the power of unit root and cointegration tests focuses both on cross sections (N) and, more remarkably, on the extension of the time period considered (T), as evidenced by Shiller and Perron (1985) and Hakkio and Rush (1991). Stock prices are adjusted for dividends, bonuses, and stock splits. Following the assumptions of the present value model, the quarterly dividend series per share correspond to 3 months, while the quarterly series of prices correspond to the end of the frequency. Similarly, the annual series of dividends per share correspond to 12 months and the quarterly series of prices correspond to the end of the frequency. All monetary values have been collected from the Economatica consulting platform and deflated by the IGP-DI index of July 31st, 2009. Thus, real terms converted by price inflation index (rpi_t) have been used and no distortion is generated by any inflationary effect.

The sample selection criteria established for Brazilian stocks are: i) to belong or to have belonged to the theoretical portfolio over the period of 1986 to 2009, ii) to have observations comprising the initial and final sampling period adopted, assuming that the present value model can be more effective when applied to companies in a stage of maturity in their life cycle. The IBOVESPA is the most important indicator of the average performance of stocks for the Brazilian stock market, having not suffered any modifications since its

inception in 1968. This index is the current value, in actual cash, of a theoretical portfolio of shares constituted on January 2nd, 1968 (basis value: 100 points) from a hypothetical application. The assumption is based on no additional investments since then, considering only adjustments made to the distribution of dividends by the issuing companies.

The following IBOVESPA companies have been analyzed for the evaluation of the present value model with constant and time-varying expected returns from unit root and cointegration techniques for nonstationary panels: ALPA3, ALPA4, AMBV4, ARCZ6, BBAS3, BBDC3, BBDC4, BDLL4, BRGE12, BRIV3, BRIV4, BRKM5, CESP5, CGRA4, CIQU4, CMIG4, CNFB4, CRUZ3, DURA4, ELUM4, ESTR4, EUCA4, FESA4, FJTA4, GOAU4, GUAR3, ILMD4, ITSA4, ITUB3, ITUB4, KLBN3, KLBN4, LAME3, LAME4, LEVE4, LIGT3, MGEL4, PETR3, PETR4, PMAM4, PMET6, RPAD6, SDIA4, SUZB5, TLPP3, TLPP4, TUPY4, UBBR3, UBBR4, VAGV4, VALE3, VALE5, VCPA4. Stock quotes have been updated to changes due to financial events such as M&A.

4.1 Present Value Model: Constant Expected Returns

In order to verify whether the real prices and real dividends series are $I(1)$ nonstationary, we apply unit root tests to the restricted model (no exogenous variable), also allowing for individual effects (individual intercept), individual effects and individual linear trends (intercept and trend). The sensitivity of the results is verified in the presence of individual effects and individual linear trends, as well as for P specific lags in orders from 0 to 4, as presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Considering all tests for the presence of a unit root in the real price series of the companies composing the panel, tests show sensitivity to the presence of individual effects and individual linear trends as well as to the lag order. The apparent ambivalence of the tests is expected and also verified in Goddard *et al.* (2008). Reverting the null hypothesis in order to test for stationarity in all companies using the Hadri test along with the Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat, in both individual models with intercept and intercept and trend, the null hypothesis of no unit root is rejected at the 1% level, not confirming that $p_{it}/rpi_t \sim I(0)$, noting that real prices as stationary processes present no theoretical support. Hence, there is an inclination to the failure of rejecting the hypothesis that the real price series of the companies surveyed have a unit root for the entire panel or for most companies analyzed, considering the different null and alternative hypotheses tested.

[TABLE 1]

We proceed with the panel unit root tests applied to the dependent variable of the PVM. Tests also show sensitivity to the presence of individual effects and individual linear trends and the lag order. Using the Hadri test along with the Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat, in both individual models with intercept and intercept and trend, the null hypothesis of no unit root is rejected at the 1% level, not confirming that $d_{it}/rpi_t \sim I(0)$, noting that real dividends as stationary processes present no theoretical support. Thus, we cannot reject the hypothesis that the real dividends series of the companies surveyed are integrated of order one for the entire panel or for most sample companies, considering the different null and alternative hypotheses tested.

[TABLE 2]

The results for panel cointegration tests are presented in Tables 3, 4 and 5. We apply the residual Kao (1999) tests and multiple Pedroni (1997, 1999, 2000, 2004) tests, both based

on Engle-Granger. Regarding the Kao (1999) residual tests, under the model with individual intercept, we reject the hypothesis of no cointegration by the automatic lag selection criterion. Analyzing the sensitivity of the results, we reject the hypothesis of no cointegration for all lag orders.

[TABLE 3]

Concerning the Pedroni (1997, 1999, 2000, 2004) tests, although they display residual sensitivity to the inclusion of linear trends and the lag order established, the prevalence is evident in relation to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration between prices and dividends considering the companies examined, hence validating the PVM with constant expected returns.

[TABLE 4]

Regarding the trace test and maximum eigenvalue of Johansen-Fisher panel data, in the absence of trend in data, the model with intercept (no trend) in CE and VAR – particularly suitable for the PVM analysis – rejects the hypothesis of zero cointegrating relationship in both statistical tests based on the trace and maximum eigenvalue at the 1% level; concerning the hypothesis of at most 1 cointegrating vector, it is also rejected in both trace and maximum eigenvalue statistics at the 1% level. This is in line with the hypothesis that real prices and real dividends exhibit a stationary relationship.

[TABLE 5]

Individual FMOLS and DOLS estimates and t -statistics are reported for $H_0: \beta_i = 0,05$. In Table 6, results are reported for panel estimators in the presence and absence of time dummies. Assuming a constant discount rate of 5%, the results from both individual tests and panel tests reject the null hypothesis at the 1% level. Concerning tests applied to individual companies, 45 out of 53 companies produce rejections in DOLS and/or FMOLS tests. For panel tests, all 6 reported results reject the null at the 1% level. Discount rate estimates are below the value of 5% per year for most series. Thus, results indicate that stock prices overstate dividend movements throughout the sample period. Panel values obtained demonstrate a relatively accurate representation of the average long-term relationship between real prices and real dividends in the present value model under constant expected returns.

[TABLE 6]

4.2 Present Value Model: Time-Varying Expected Returns

In order to verify whether the real log prices and real log dividends series are $I(1)$ nonstationary in the present value model under time-varying expected returns, we apply unit root tests to the restricted model (no exogenous variable), also allowing for individual effects (individual intercept) and individual effects and individual linear trends (intercept and trend). Analogously to the previous section, the sensitivity of the results is verified in the presence of individual effects and individual linear trends, as well as for P specific lags in orders from 0 to 4, as presented in Tables 7 and 8.

Considering all tests for the presence of unit root in the real log price series of companies composing the panel, tests show sensitivity to the presence of individual effects and individual linear trends as well as to lag order. The apparent ambivalence of the tests is

expected and also found in Goddard *et al.* (2008), in which the diagnosis of $I(0)$ stationarity or $I(1)$ nonstationarity depends on whether or not the trend is included, as well as upon the order of the lag established. Reverting the null hypothesis in order to test for stationarity in all companies using the Hadri test along with the Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat, in both individual models with intercept and intercept and trend, the null hypothesis of no unit root is rejected at the 1% level, not confirming that $\ln(p_{it}/rpi_t) \sim I(0)$, noting that real log prices as stationary processes present no theoretical support. Hence, there is an inclination to the failure of rejecting the hypothesis that the real log prices series of the companies surveyed are integrated of order one for the entire panel or for most companies comprising it, considering the different null and alternative hypotheses tested.

[TABLE 7]

In Table 8, we examine the panel unit root tests applied to the real log dividend series $\ln(d_{it}/rpi_t)$. The diagnosis of $I(0)$ stationarity or nonstationarity $I(1)$ shows sensitivity to the inclusion or exclusion of trend as well as to the lag order established. Using the Hadri test along with the Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat, in both individual models with intercept and intercept and trend, the null hypothesis of no unit root is rejected at the 1% level, not confirming that $\ln(d_{it}/rpi_t) \sim I(0)$, noting that real log dividends as stationary processes present no theoretical support. Thus, we cannot reject the hypothesis that the real log dividends series of the sample companies have a unit root for the entire panel or for most companies comprising it, considering the different null and alternative hypotheses tested.

[TABLE 8]

In order to test the validity of PVM with time-varying expected returns, it is expected that the log price-dividend ratio is $I(0)$ stationary, as discussed in the presented literature. In relation to the panel unit root tests applied to the log price-dividend ratio $\ln(p_{it}/d_{it})$ in Table 9, we cannot reject the hypothesis that the log price-dividend series of the companies examined is stationary for the entire panel or for most companies surveyed. Hence, we cannot reject the PVM with time-varying expected returns from the panel unit root tests applied.

[TABLE 9]

Once verified that log real prices and log real dividends are predominantly $I(1)$, we apply the panel cointegration tests. The results are presented in Tables 10, 11 and 12. As in the previous section, we employ the residual Kao (1999) and multiple Pedroni (1997, 1999, 2000, 2004) tests based on Engle-Granger. Regarding the Kao (1999) tests, under the model with individual intercept, we fail to reject the hypothesis of no cointegration by the automatic lag selection criterion. Analyzing the sensitivity of the results, we reject the hypothesis of no cointegration only for fixed lag of order 1.

[TABLE 10]

Examining the Pedroni (1997, 1999, 2000, 2004) tests, although they display residual sensitivity to the inclusion of linear trends and the lag order established, the prevalence is evident in relation to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration between log real prices and log real dividends, considering the companies examined, hence validating the PVM with time-varying expected returns.

[TABLE 11]

Regarding the Maddala and Wu (1999) cointegration tests that combine the p -values from the trace test and maximum eigenvalue of Johansen-Fisher, in the model with intercept (no trend) in CE and VAR – particularly suitable for the PVM analysis – we reject the hypothesis of zero cointegrating relationships in both statistics based on the trace test and maximum eigenvalue at the 1% level; in relation to the hypothesis of at most 1 cointegrating vector, it is also rejected in both trace statistics and maximum eigenvalue at the 1% level.

Thus, from panel cointegration tests of Kao (1999), Pedroni (1997, 1999, 2000, 2004) and Maddala and Wu (1999), we cannot reject the hypothesis of no cointegration between real log prices and real log dividends, considering the sample companies examined, validating, therefore, the present value model between prices and dividends with time-varying expected returns developed seminally in Campbell and Shiller (1988a,b).

[TABLE 12]

The present value model holds when logged prices and dividends are cointegrated and $\beta_i = 1$. A one-for-one cointegrating equilibrium implies that the price-dividend ratio is stationary. Regressing dividends on price, if overvaluation is defined as stock price movements neither backed nor justified by dividend movements, stocks are overvalued if $\beta_i < 1$. Inversely, if $\beta_i > 1$, stocks are considered undervalued. Individual FMOLS and DOLS estimates and t -statistics are reported for $H_0: \beta_i = 1$. In Table 13, results are reported for panel estimators in the presence and absence of time dummies. Assuming a time-varying discount rate of 5%, the results from both individual and panel tests predominantly reject the null hypothesis between the 1% and 10% levels and parameters obtained evidence overvaluation of real prices for most sample companies.

[TABLE 13]

5. CONCLUSION

The empirical evidence on the long-term relationship between stock prices and dividends remain scarce. As stock prices rose, analysts questioned whether the fundamental value of a share related to innovations in dividends, since low dividend payouts and record-high stock prices suggested an overvaluation. From then on, the validity of the Present Value Model (PVM) started to be debated, because the recent collapse of stock prices underline the importance of traditional measures in the valuation of stocks, since they relate stock prices to the fundamental value of corporations.

While most studies focusing on the relationship between prices and dividends have examined the long-term relationship between a stock price index and an index of dividends of a particular country of interest, the empirical analysis in this paper is based on prices and dividends at the firm level through first generation panel unit root and panel cointegration estimation methods to test the long-term relationship between stock prices and dividends for the Brazilian stock market. The use of firm level data allows the analysis of patterns and relationships that can be obscured at the aggregate stock market level through averaging in the aggregation process. Thus, the power increase and precision obtained by the procedures allow the application of recent data, as well as possible structural changes in the data that occur more frequently over longer periods, and the more accurate assessment regarding the consistency of the present value model under considerable fluctuations in the stock market.

Regarding the results obtained in the Present Value Model with Constant Expected Returns, from the panel unit root tests, the statistics show sensitivity to the presence of individual effects and individual linear trends and to the lag order. The ambivalent results of the tests are expected and also found in Goddard *et al.* (2008). However, there is an inclination to the failure of rejecting the hypothesis that real prices and real dividends series have a unit root for the entire panel or for most companies surveyed, considering the different null and alternative hypotheses tested. From the panel cointegration tests of Kao (1999), Pedroni (1997, 1999, 2000, 2004) and Maddala and Wu (1999), results fail to reject the hypothesis of no cointegration between real prices and real dividends considering the different sample companies examined, validating, therefore, the Present Value Model between prices and dividends with Constant Expected Returns developed seminally in Campbell and Shiller (1987).

Analyzing the Present Value Model with Time-Varying Expected Returns, the apparent ambivalence of the unit root tests is expected and verified, in which the diagnosis of $I(0)$ stationarity or nonstationarity $I(1)$ depends on whether or not the trend is included, as well as upon the lag order established. However, results cannot reject the hypothesis that real log prices and real log dividends series have a unit root for the entire panel or for most companies comprising it, considering the different null and alternative hypotheses tested. In accordance to the theory, results do not reject that log price-dividend ratio is a $I(0)$ stationary process, indicating the validity of the Present Value Model. Finally, from the cointegration tests for panel data, statistical results cannot reject the hypothesis of cointegration between real prices and real dividends, considering the different sample companies observed, hence validating the Present Value Model between prices and dividends with Time-Varying Expected Returns developed seminally in Campbell and Shiller (1988a,b).

Finally, it is presented that, for panel cointegrated regression models, the asymptotic properties of the estimators of the regression coefficients and the associated statistical tests are different from those of the time series cointegration regression models. Panel cointegration models direct to the assessment of long-term relationships verified in macroeconomic and financial data. Thus, results from the FMOLS and DOLS estimators applied to cointegrated panels, individual companies show evidence of overvaluation of stock prices for most examined companies, assuming either the hypothesis of constant or time-varying expected returns.

REFERENCES

- Anchite, C. F., & Issler, J. V. (2001, apr). Racionalidade e previsibilidade no mercado brasileiro de ações: uma aplicação de modelos de valor presente. *Ensaio Econômicos* .
- Balke, N. S., & Wohar, M. E. (2002). Low-frequency movements in stock prices: a state-space decomposition. *The Review of Economics and Statistics* , 84 (4), pp. 649-667.
- Breitung, J. (2000). The local power of some unit root tests for panel data. (B. BALTAGI, Ed.) *JAI Press* , 15 (Advances in Econometrics), pp. 161-178.
- Brooks, C., & Katsaris, A. (2003). Rational speculative bubbles: an empirical investigation of the London stock exchange. *Bulletin of Economic Research* , 55, pp. 319-346.
- Campbell, J. Y., & Shiller, R. J. (1987). Cointegration and testes of present value models. *Journal of Political Economy* , 95 (5), pp. 1062-1088.

Campbell, J. Y., & Shiller, R. J. (1988a). The dividend-price ratio and expectations of future dividends and discount factors. *Review of financial Studies* , 1 (3), pp. 195-228.

Campbell, J. Y., & Shiller, R. J. (1988b). Stock prices, earnings, and expected dividends. *Journal of Finance* , 3, pp. 661-676.

Cecchetti, S. G., Lam, P. S., & Mark, N. C. (1990, jun). Mean reversion in equilibrium asset prices. *The American Economic Review* , 80 (3), pp. 398-348.

Cohen, R. B., Polk, C., & Vuolteenaho, T. (2001, apr). The value spread. *NBER Working Paper* .

Diba, B. T., & Grossman, H. I. (1988, jun). Explosive rational bubbles in stock prices? *American Economic Review* , 3, pp. 520-530.

Dupuis, D., & Tessier, D. (2003). The U.S. Market and fundamentals: a historical decomposition. *Bank of Canada Working Paper* , 20.

Fama, E. F., & French, K. R. (1988, apr). Permanent and temporary components of stock prices. *Journal of Political Economy* , 96 (2), pp. 246-273.

Froot, K., & Obstfeld, M. (1991, dec). Intrinsic bubbles: the case of stock prices. *American Economy Review* , 81 (5), pp. 1189-1214.

Goddard, J., McMillan, D. G., & Wilsin, J. O. (2008, apr). Dividends, prices and the present value model: firm-level evidence. *European Journal of Finance* , 14 (3), pp. 195-210.

Hadri, K. (2000). Testing for stationarity in heterogeneous panel data. *Econometrics Journal* , 3 (2), pp. 148-161.

Hakkio, C. S., & Rush, M. (1991). Cointegration: how short is the long-run? *Journal of international Money and Finance* , 10 (4), pp. 578-581.

Im, K. S., Pesaran, M. H., & Shin, Y. (2003). Testing for unit roots in heterogeneous panels. *Journal of Econometrics* , 115, pp. 53-74.

Jung, J., & Shiller, R. J. (2005). Samuelson's dictum and the stock market. *Rconomic Inquiry* , 43 (2), p. 221.

Kao, C. (1999). Spurious regression and residual-based tests for cointegration in panel data. *Journal of Economics* , 90, pp. 1-44.

Kapetanios, G., Shin, Y., & Snell, A. (2006). Testing for cointegration in nonlinear smooth transition error-correction models. *Econometric Theory* , 22, pp. 279-303.

Kim, C., Morley, J. C., & Nelson, C. (2001). Does an intertemporal trade off between risk and return explain mean reversion in stock prices? *Journal of Empirical Finance* , 8, pp. 403-426.

Lamont, O. (1998). Earnings and expected returns. *Journal of Finance* , 53, pp. 1563-1587.

- Levin, A., & Lin, C. F. (1993). An empirical investigation of the long-run behavior of real exchange rates. *Carnegie-Rochester Conference Series on Public Policy* , 27, pp. 149-214.
- Levin, A., Lin, C. F., & Chu, C. S. (2002). Unit root tests in panel data: asymptotic and finite-sample properties. *Journal of Econometrics* , 108, pp. 1-24.
- Maddala, G. S., & Wu, S. A. (1999). Comparative study of unit root tests with panel data and a new simple test. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics* , 61, pp. 631-652.
- Manzan, S. (2004). Nonlinear mean reversion in stock prices. *CeNDEF Working Paper 03-02* , Department of Quantitative Economics (University of Amsterdam).
- Morales, J. C. (2006). Modelos de valor presente sob a hipótese de eficiência no mercado acionário brasileiro. *Dissertação* , Faculdade Ibmecc, SP, Brazil.
- Nasseh, A., & Straus, J. (2004, may). Stock prices and the dividend discount model: did their relation break down in the 1990s. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance* , 44 (2), pp. 191-207.
- Pedroni, P. (1996, jun). Fully modified OLS for heterogeneous cointegrated panels and the case of purchasing power parity. *Indiana University Working Papers in Economics* , 96-020.
- Pedroni, P. (1997). Panel cointegration: asymptotic and finite sample properties of pooled time series with an application to the PPP hypothesis: new results. Working Paper, Indiana University.
- Pedroni, P. (1999). Values for cointegration tests in heterogeneous panels with multiple regressors. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics* , 61, pp. 653-670.
- Pedroni, P. (2000). Fully modified OLS for heterogeneous cointegrated panels. *Advances in Econometrics* , 15, pp. 93-130.
- Pedroni, P. (2001). Purchasing power parity tests in cointegrated panels. 83 (4), pp. 727-731.
- Pedroni, P. (2004). Asymptotic and finite sample properties of pooled time series tests with an application to the PPP hypothesis. *Econometric Theory* , 20 (3), pp. 597-625.
- Shiller, R. J., & Perron, P. (1985). Testing the random walk hypothesis: power versus frequency of observation. *Economics Letters* , 18, pp. 381-386.
- Su, C., Chang, H., & Chen, Y. (2007). Stock prices and dividends in Taiwan's stock market: evidence based on time-varying present value model. *Economics Bulletin* , 7 (4).
- Timmermann, A. (1995). Cointegration tests of present value models with a time-varying discount factor. *Journal of Applied Econometrics* , 10, pp. 17-31.
- Vuolteenaho, T. (2002). What drives firm-level stock returns? *Journal of finance* , 57, pp. 233-264.

Table 1 – Panel Unit Root Tests: p_{it}/rpi_t

Model	Restricted		Individual Intercept		Intercept and Trend	
	Automatic Lag Length Selection (AIC): 0 to 4					
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*	-2,28321	[0.0112]**	18,5787	1.0000	15.2497	1,0000
Breitung t -stat	-	-	-	-	3.39507	0,9997
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat	-	-	2.07979	0,9812	-6,05231	[0.0000]***
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square	173.188	[0.0000]***	175.762	[0.0000]***	270.642	[0.0000]***
Choi-ADF Z-stat	1.70995	0.9564	2.61528	0.9955	-4,64084	[0.0000]***
Fixed Lags						
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*						
0	-3,15259	[0.0008]***	-2,8701	[0.0021]***	-6,88928	[0.0000]***
1	-3,29338	[0.0005]***	-1,62736	[0.0518]*	-5,80197	[0.0000]***
2	-40,6773	[0.0000]***	-84,909	[0.0000]***	-92,9979	[0.0000]***
3	1.15754	0,8765	22,4429	1,0000	23,6944	1,0000
4	-2,7979	[0.0026]***	28,2651	1,0000	38,5565	1,0000
Breitung t -stat						
0	-	-	-	-	2.66591	0.9962
1	-	-	-	-	3,7066	0,9999
2	-	-	-	-	3,27428	0,9995
3	-	-	-	-	3,03404	0,9988
4	-	-	-	-	3,50573	0,9998
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat						
0	-	-	-1,21187	0,1128	-4,44501	[0.0000]***
1	-	-	1.12969	0,8707	-2,52375	0.0058
2	-	-	-15,5425	[0.0000]***	-18,1787	[0.0000]***
3	-	-	5.83310	1.0000	2.08716	0.9816
4	-	-	2.96120	0.9985	-0,11022	0,4561
Im-Pesaran-Shin t -bar						
0	-	-	-1,6744	-	[-2.69762]***	-
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square						
0	155.645	[0.0012]***	128.116	[0.0708]*	164.667	[0.0002]***
1	198,022	[0.0000]***	170.933	[0.0001]***	198.728	[0.0000]***
2	146,951	[0.0052]***	622.184	[0.0000]***	167,685	[0.0001]***
3	72,7228	0.9944	61.0590	0.9999	88,0442	0,8969
4	110,494	0.3631	118.111	0.1984	122,531	0.1300
Choi-ADF Z-stat						
0	-2,90113	[0.0019]***	-1,18919	0.1172	-4,47871	[0.0000]***
1	-0,54853	0.2917	1,15898	0,8768	-1,92918	[0.0269]**
2	2,22608	0.987	1.40693	0.9203	1,18908	0.8828
3	4,80871	1.0000	6,86059	1.0000	3,36174	0.9996
4	3.43865	0.9997	5.42836	1.0000	2.85895	0.9979
Fisher-PP Chi-Square	157.507	[0.0009]***	129.710	[0.0587]*	199.409	[0.0000]***
Choi-PP Z-stat	-2,34682	[0.0095]***	-0,87072	0.1920	-4,85371	[0.0000]***
Ho: Stationarity (common unit root process)						
Hadri Z-stat	-	-	18.1880	[0.0000]***	12.9798	[0.0000]***
Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat	-	-	14.1587	[0.0000]***	14.2305	[0.0000]***

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality. LLC, Fisher-PP and Hadri: Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel. Critical t -bar values obtained from original Im, Pesaran e Shin (2003) paper. In Hadri test, high correlation leads to severe size distortion, leading to over-rejection of the null.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 2 – Panel Unit Root Tests: d_{it}/rpi_t

Model	Restricted		Individual Intercept		Intercept and Trend	
	Automatic Lag Length Selection (AIC): 0 to 4					
Método	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*	-4,6888	[0.0000]***	-3,3710	[0.0004]***	4,89877	1.0000
Breitung t -stat	-	-	-	-	1,4064	0,9202
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat	-	-	-5,7001	[0.0000]***	-8,0994	[0.0000]***
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square	241.778	[0.0000]***	470.940	[0.0000]***	435.803	[0.0000]***
Choi-ADF Z-stat	-2,7398	[0.0031]***	-4,2926	[0.0000]***	-6,8387	[0.0000]***
Fixed Lags						
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*						
0	-25,0438	[0.0000]***	-32,2061	[0.0000]***	-32,5282	[0.0000]***
1	-8,0673	[0.0000]***	-0,4760	0.3170	0,88223	0,8112
2	-40,3807	[0.0000]***	-63,1416	[0.0000]***	-74,7506	[0.0000]***
3	-1,0754	0.1411	33,4245	1,0000	40,7919	1,0000
4	0,37535	0.6463	57,9524	1,0000	76,3102	1,0000
Breitung t -stat						
0	-	-	-	-	-0,5127	0.3041
1	-	-	-	-	-0,1918	0,4239
2	-	-	-	-	1,5247	0,9363
3	-	-	-	-	2,1342	0,9836
4	-	-	-	-	5,36374	1,0000
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat						
0	-	-	-12,5074	[0.0000]***	-14,5772	[0.0000]***
1	-	-	-2,9645	[0.0015]***	-4,4421	[0.0000]***
2	-	-	-11,7258	[0.0000]***	-1,80E+16	[0.0000]***
3	-	-	0,65700	0.7444	-2,3310	[0.0099]***
4	-	-	1,8240	0.9659	-1,5334	[0.0626]*
Im-Pesaran-Shin t -bar						
0	-	-	[-3.09863]***	-	[-3.90533]***	-
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square						
0	280,0190	[0.0000]***	729.654	[0.0000]***	707,1940	[0.0000]***
1	250,812	[0.0000]***	216,1470	[0.0000]***	191,5430	[0.0000]***
2	188,2920	[0.0000]***	551,1020	[0.0000]***	191.766	[0.0000]***
3	138.618	[0.0132]**	182,3680	[0.0000]***	124.286	0.0854
4	103,6260	0.4919	83,0211	0.9356	102.511	0.5229
Choi-ADF Z-stat						
0	-6,4754	[0.0000]***	-8,3971	[0.0000]***	-10,3793	[0.0000]***
1	-3,8159	[0.0001]***	-2,2270	[0.0130]**	-4,0754	[0.0000]***
2	-1,3397	[0.0902]*	-2,4336	[0.0075]***	NA	-
3	0,64932	0.7419	2,14441	0.9840	-0,3380	0.3677
4	2,43557	0.9926	3,96827	1.0000	0,7964	0.7871
Fisher-PP Chi-Square	275.028	[0.0000]***	779.714	[0.0000]***	797.972	[0.0000]***
Choi-PP Z-stat	-4,9376	[0.0000]***	-8,3378	[0.0000]***	-11,5246	[0.0000]***
Ho: Stationarity (common unit root process)						
Hadri Z-stat	-	-	4.64082	[0.0000]***	9.70268	[0.0000]***
Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat	-	-	12.9789	[0.0000]***	10.9717	[0.0000]***

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality. LLC, Fisher-PP and Hadri: Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel. Critical t -bar values obtained from original Im, Pesaran e Shin (2003) paper. In Hadri test, high correlation leads to severe size distortion, leading to over-rejection of the null.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 3 – Residual-Based Kao Tests: d_{it}/rpi_t and p_{it}/rpi_t

Ho: No Cointegration								
Model with Individual Intercept								
Automatic Selection: 2 Lags based on AIC								
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))
t	-9,0846	16.22261	11.39772	-17,7954	4,3092	0,0638	-	-
Prob.	[0.0000]***	-	-	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	0,0270	-	-
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0,6437	0,1413	2,3615	-	-
Std. Error	-	-	-	0,0362	0,0328	[0.0184]**	-	-
	R-squared	0,29669		Adjusted R-squared	0,295289		DW stat	1,98638
Fixed Lag: 1								
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))
t	-11,7603	16.22261	11.39772	-20,1559	3,2073	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0000]***	-	-	[0.0000]***	[0.0014]***	-	-	-
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0,6329	0,0883	-	-	-
Std. Error	-	-	-	0,0314	0,0275	-	-	-
	R-squared	0,308906		Adjusted R-squared	0,308253		DW stat	1,907819
Fixed Lag: 2								
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))
t	-9,0846	16.22261	11.39772	-17,7954	4,3092	0,0638	-	-
Prob.	[0.0000]***	-	-	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	0,0270	-	-
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0,6437	0,1413	2,3615	-	-
Std. Error	-	-	-	0,0362	0,0328	[0.0184]**	-	-
	R-squared	0,29669		Adjusted R-squared	0,295289		DW stat	1,98638
Fixed Lag: 3								
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))
t	-6,9656	16.22261	11.39772	-15,9261	5,4298	2,2780	1,9357	-
Prob.	[0.0000]***	-	-	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0230]**	[0.0532]*	-
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0,6727	0,2100	0,0765	0,0530	-
Std. Error	-	-	-	0,0422	0,0387	0,0336	0,0274	-
	R-squared	0,288156		Adjusted R-squared	0,285908		DW stat	2,11568
Fixed Lag: 4								
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))
t	-6,0687	16.22261	11.39772	-15,1347	6,0761	3,1180	3,1311	2,2518
Prob.	[0.0000]***	-	-	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0019]***	[0.0018]***	[0.0246]**
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0,7428	0,2735	0,1262	0,1082	0,0633
Std. Error	-	-	-	0,0491	0,0450	0,0405	0,0346	0,0281
	R-squared	0,296736		Adjusted R-squared	0,293597		DW stat	2,123853

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 4 – Pedroni Multiple Tests: d_{it}/rpi_t and p_{it}/rpi_t

Ho: No Cointegration							
Panel Tests				Group Tests			
v-Statistic T1	rho-Statistic T2	PP-statistic T3	ADF-statistic T4	rho-Statistic T5	PP-Statistic T6	ADF-Statistic T7	
Ha: Common AR coefficients (<i>within-dimension</i>)				Ha: Individual AR coefficients (<i>between-dimension</i>)			
Automatic Lag Length Selection: Max Lag of 4 based on AIC							
Restricted Model							
S1	14.38529	-18,8584	-17,4167	-17,3132	14,3853	-18,8584	-17,4167
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***
S2	2.879485	-12,0592	-10,7620	-9,1541	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0063]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	6.130905	-13,7506	-17,0284	-16,9181	-8,3048	-15,0771	-14,1739
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***
S2	1.205090	-11,9568	-13,1104	-12,4344	-	-	-
Prob.	0.1930	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-1,3393	-7,6167	-15,3008	-15,1543	-3,6954	-15,2276	-10,9516
Prob.	0.1627	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0004]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***
S2	-3,6644	-7,4270	-14,4561	-14,3098	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0005]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	-	-	-
Fixed Lag: 1							
Restricted Model							
S1	14.38529	-18,8584	-17,4167	-13,2967	-10,1090	-20,3044	-13,7822
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***
S2	2.879485	-12,0592	-10,7620	-7,4407	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0063]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	6.130905	-13,7506	-17,0284	-12,4387	-8,3048	-15,0771	-9,7771
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***
S2	1.205090	-11,9568	-13,1104	-8,8961	-	-	-
Prob.	0.1930	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-1,3393	-7,6167	-15,3008	-10,7284	-3,6954	-15,2276	-7,8414
Prob.	0.1627	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0004]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***
S2	-3,6644	-7,4270	-14,4561	-9,1609	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0005]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	-	-	-
Fixed Lag: 2							
Restricted Model							
S1	14.38529	-18,8584	-17,4167	-9,1231	-10,1090	-20,3044	-11,1728
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***
S2	2.879485	-12,0592	-10,7620	-4,8865	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0063]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	6.130905	-13,7506	-17,0284	-7,2586	-8,3048	-15,0771	-11,0159
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***
S2	1.205090	-11,9568	-13,1104	-3,9426	-	-	-
Prob.	0.1930	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0002]***	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-1,3393	-7,6167	-15,3008	-4,5457	-3,6954	-15,2276	-5,3517
Prob.	0.1627	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0004]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***
S2	-3,6644	-7,4270	-14,4561	-3,3787	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0005]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0013]***	-	-	-
Fixed Lag: 3							
Restricted Model							
S1	14.38529	-18,8584	-17,4167	-8,3171	-10,1090	-20,3044	-4,4068
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***
S2	2.879485	-12,0592	-10,7620	-3,5993	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0063]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0006]***	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	6.130905	-13,7506	-17,0284	-6,3291	-8,3048	-15,0771	-0,6857
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	0.3154
S2	1.205090	-11,9568	-13,1104	-1,6541	-	-	-
Prob.	0.1930	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	0.1016	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-1,3393	-7,6167	-15,3008	-4,0621	-3,6954	-15,2276	0,872635
Prob.	0.1627	0.0000	[0.0000]***	[0.0001]***	[0.0004]***	[0.0000]***	0.2726
S2	-3,6644	-7,4270	-14,4561	-0,8348	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0005]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	0.2816	-	-	-
Fixed Lag: 4							
Restricted Model							
S1	14.38529	-18,8584	-17,4167	-5,8145	-10,1090	-20,3044	-2,8177
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0075]***
S2	2.879485	-12,0592	-10,7620	-2,0921	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0063]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0447]**	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	6.130905	-13,7506	-17,0284	-3,6216	-8,3048	-15,0771	0.391604
Prob.	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	[0.0006]***	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]**	0.3695
S2	1.205090	-11,9568	-13,1104	-0,7975	-	-	-
Prob.	0.1930	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	0.2903	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-1,3393	-7,6167	-15,3008	-1,1543	-3,6954	-15,2276	2.419183
Prob.	0.1627	[0.0000]***	[0.0000]***	0.2049	[0.0004]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0214]**
S2	-3,6644	-7,4270	-14,4561	0.403012	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0005]***	[0.0000]**	[0.0000]***	0.3678	-	-	-

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. S1 represents the statistics, and S2 denotes the weighted statistics. Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 5 – Panel Johansen-Fisher Test: d_{it}/rpi_t and p_{it}/rpi_t

Deterministic Trend Specification: No Trend in Data				
No Intercept or trend in CE or VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	430.4	[0.0000]***	408.0	[0.0000]***
At most 1	174.9	[0.0000]***	174.9	[0.0000]***
Intercept (no trend) in CE - no intercept in VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	372.7	[0.0000]***	386.5	[0.0000]***
At most 1	115.5	0.2488	115.5	0.2488
Deterministic Trend Specification: Linear Trend in Data				
Intercept (no trend) in CE and VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	427.3	[0.0000]***	406.5	[0.0000]***
At most 1	237.9	[0.0000]***	237.9	[0.0000]***
Intercept and trend in CE - no trend in VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	909.2	[0.0000]***	362.5	[0.0000]***
At most 1	118.8	0.1869	118.8	0.1869
Deterministic Trend Specification: Quadratic Trend in Data				
Intercept and trend in CE - linear trend in VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	451.8	[0.0000]***	413.7	[0.0000]***
At most 1	398.7	[0.0000]***	398.7	[0.0000]***

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Lags interval (in first differences): 1 1. Probabilities are computed using asymptotic χ^2 distribution.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 6 – Panel Cointegration Estimates: Constant Returns

$$\frac{d_{it}}{rpi_t} = \alpha_i + \beta_i \frac{p_{it}}{rpi_t} + \mu_{it}$$

Firm	Dynamic Lags = 0				Dynamic Lags = 1			
	FMOLS	<i>t</i> -stat	DOLS	<i>t</i> -stat	FMOLS	<i>t</i> -stat	DOLS	<i>t</i> -stat
	Lags = 0				Lags = 1			
ALPA3	0,0224	[-3.3861]**	0,0227	[-3.9488]**	0,0221	[-3.6122]**	0,0377	-1,0484
ALPA4	0,0233	[-2.5495]*	0,0232	[-3.1482]**	0,0229	[-2.7870]**	0,0284	-1,0037
AMBV4	0,0333	[-3.6487]**	0,0319	[-2.9639]**	0,0328	[-3.5077]**	0,0266	[-3.3076]**
ARCZ6	0,0532	0,4234	0,0560	0,8633	0,0547	0,5700	0,0591	1,1756
BBAS3	0,0771	0,2245	0,0881	0,4263	0,0780	0,2765	0,1875	1,3684
BBDC3	0,0205	[-4.0496]**	0,0178	[-4.5422]**	0,0181	[-4.4288]**	0,0420	-0,4380
BBDC4	0,0207	[-5.4902]**	0,0206	[-7.4430]**	0,0205	[-6.2854]**	0,0305	[-1.6694]*
BDLL4	0,1010	0,7823	0,1199	1,4197	0,1070	1,0605	0,1797	[1.7606]*
BRGE12	0,0263	-1,0147	0,0352	-0,9175	0,0314	-0,9343	0,0333	-0,8817
BRIV3	0,0370	-0,9631	0,0382	-1,0746	0,0383	-0,9683	0,0360	-0,7645
BRIV4	0,0427	-0,3530	0,0461	-0,2607	0,0460	-0,2179	0,0276	-0,9777
BRKM5	-0,0454	[-3.4354]**	-0,0156	[-2.4764]*	-0,0357	[-3.0442]**	-0,0618	[-3.8037]**
CESP5	0,0862	0,9019	0,0852	0,8702	0,0815	0,8689	0,0928	0,7471
CGRA4	0,0259	[-2.9474]**	0,0223	[-3.7062]**	0,0233	[-3.3480]**	0,0903	1,1403
CIQU4	0,0156	[-1.9493]*	0,0100	[-3.2441]**	0,0135	[-2.4498]*	-0,0023	[-2.1362]*
CMIG4	0,0852	[2.4827]*	0,0935	[2.7679]**	0,0896	[2.4324]*	0,1070	[2.7045]**
CNFB4	0,0272	[-2.0469]*	0,0260	[-2.5553]*	0,0265	[-2.4519]*	0,0182	-0,8994
CRUZ3	0,0325	-0,4706	0,0330	-0,6982	0,0327	-0,5892	-0,0071	-0,9648
DURA4	0,0160	[-6.5739]**	0,0214	[-5.7101]**	0,0167	[-6.1155]**	0,0138	[-3.0427]**
ELUM4	0,0218	[-9.8799]**	0,0211	[-9.8381]**	0,0234	[-9.8001]**	0,0066	[-16.7888]**
ESTR4	0,0142	[-32.1986]**	0,0144	[-43.4016]**	0,0152	[-34.0188]**	0,0012	[-11.4884]**
EUCA4	0,0065	[-11.0626]**	0,0072	[-12.3620]**	0,0072	[-12.5017]**	0,0119	[-11.3127]**
FESA4	0,0633	[1.9392]*	0,0709	[2.8449]**	0,0663	[2.1305]*	0,0555	0,6637
FJTA4	0,2096	1,0334	0,2626	[2.1027]*	0,2499	1,4805	0,3519	[5.1510]**
GOAU4	0,0456	-0,8116	0,0454	-0,9881	0,0454	-0,9192	0,0265	[-1.8104]*
GUAR3	0,0053	[-19.7628]**	0,0054	[-31.5773]**	0,0054	[-22.9544]**	0,0108	[-9.5412]**
ILMD4	0,0688	0,2087	0,3263	[3.7723]**	0,1355	0,8443	0,3686	[5.9974]**
ITSA4	0,0329	[-3.0462]**	0,0319	[-4.1667]**	0,0324	[-3.4372]**	0,0658	1,3125
ITUB3	0,0339	[-4.3536]**	0,0341	[-6.2169]**	0,0338	[-3.7098]**	0,0343	[-2.9640]**
ITUB4	0,0297	[-6.1577]**	0,0298	[-8.5246]**	0,0297	[-5.2947]**	0,0323	[-3.5804]**
KLBN3	0,0222	[-3.5857]**	0,0246	[-3.3626]**	0,0220	[-3.6931]**	0,0058	[-2.0344]*
KLBN4	0,0693	[2.6487]**	0,0751	[3.2236]**	0,0696	[2.4078]*	0,0638	[1.7888]*
LAME3	0,0087	[-9.8630]**	0,0057	[-11.9046]**	0,0071	[-10.5523]**	-0,0077	[-3.3622]**
LAME4	0,0092	[-8.3612]**	0,0059	[-11.0988]**	0,0072	[-9.2447]**	-0,0402	[-4.8859]**
LEVE4	0,1419	[2.6094]**	0,1356	[2.2421]*	0,1523	[2.7721]**	0,2004	[3.3299]**
LJGT3	0,1327	[1.7275]*	0,1542	[2.9109]**	0,1389	[1.8008]*	0,1530	[2.2736]*
MGEL4	0,0055	[-5.8261]**	0,0183	[-4.5448]**	0,0084	[-5.5982]**	0,0168	[-4.1387]**
PETR3	0,0282	[-3.4916]**	0,0268	[-5.0753]**	0,0277	[-4.3297]**	0,0890	[3.7582]**
PETR4	0,0335	[-2.3070]*	0,0311	[-3.5584]**	0,0325	[-2.9523]**	0,0898	[3.7166]**
PMAM4	0,1506	[1.8054]*	0,1813	[2.4388]*	0,1608	[1.9848]*	0,4314	[3.8640]**
PMET6	0,0324	[-1.9792]*	0,0413	-1,2196	0,0372	-1,5961	0,0440	-0,6737
RPAD6	0,0299	-0,9200	0,0381	-0,7855	0,0357	-0,7684	0,0438	-0,3472
SDIA4	0,0292	[-3.2459]**	0,0260	[-3.1614]**	0,0268	[-3.2916]**	0,0193	[-2.9260]**
SUZB5	0,0268	[-2.6132]**	0,0230	[-3.0640]**	0,0223	[-3.0467]**	0,0216	[-2.0766]*
TLPP3	0,1952	[2.5782]**	0,1757	[2.8771]**	0,1865	[2.6723]**	0,2666	[3.2309]**
TLPP4	0,2016	[3.6590]**	0,2015	[4.0717]**	0,2036	[3.8352]**	0,2513	[4.2697]**
TUPY4	0,0213	[-45.3178]**	0,0216	[-44.2334]**	0,0217	[-45.5614]**	0,0081	[-6.6396]**
UBBR3	0,0167	[-20.4276]**	0,0155	[-19.9432]**	0,0160	[-19.6128]**	0,0194	[-10.6809]**
UBBR4	0,0384	[-2.8530]**	0,0375	[-3.0158]**	0,0378	[-3.2001]**	0,0524	0,3571
VAGV4	0,1414	1,5291	0,1599	[1.6924]*	0,1492	[1.8271]*	0,1210	0,6734
VALE3	0,0199	[-6.3231]**	0,0192	[-9.1246]**	0,0191	[-7.5069]**	0,0259	-1,1686
VALE5	0,0223	[-5.6007]**	0,0221	[-7.9303]**	0,0219	[-6.5931]**	0,0534	0,1165
VCPA4	0,0442	-0,7152	0,0458	-0,4119	0,0456	-0,4350	0,0668	[2.7539]**

Panel Results

	Without Time Dummies							
<i>Between</i>	0,0501	[-30.9000]**	0,0587	[-35.3943]**	0,0531	[-32.1966]**	0,0736	[-8.9565]**
	With Time Dummies							
<i>Between</i>	0,0310	[-14.7497]**	0,0408	[-15.0615]**	0,0348	[-14.8422]**	0,0359	[-9.4386]**

Note: *t*-stats refer to $H_0: \beta_i = 0,05$, assuming a constant discount rate of 5%. *, ** indicate rejection levels of 10%, 1%. “Between” reports the group-mean panel FMOLS from Pedroni (1996) and group-mean panel DOLS from Pedroni (2001).

Table 7 – Panel Unit Root Tests: $\ln(p_{it}/rpi_t)$

Model	Restricted		Individual Intercept		Intercept and Trend	
	Automatic Lag Length Selection (AIC): 0 to 4					
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*	-0,2571	0.3986	-9,9786	[0.0000]***	-4,9128	[0.0000]***
Breitung t -stat	-	-	-	-	-3,8620	[0.0001]***
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat	-	-	-3,2532	[0.0006]***	-3,0595	[0.0011]***
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square	44,2570	0.2244	74,6544	[0.0004]***	65.1216	[0.004]***
Choi-ADF Z-stat	-0,2327	0.4080	-2,6553	[0.0040]***	-2,8838	[0.002]***
Fixed Lags						
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*						
0	-0,9670	0.1668	-4,8287	[0.0000]***	-5,2323	[0.0000]***
1	0,4396	0.6699	-3,7322	[0.0001]***	-3,3773	[0.0004]***
2	1.26903	0.8978	-2,9644	[0.0015]***	-0,8664	0.1932
3	-1,2171	0.1118	-13,6157	[0.0000]***	-5,5994	[0.0000]***
4	0.53430	0.7034	-9,3469	[0.0000]***	-2,8954	[0.0019]***
Breitung t -stat						
0	-	-	-	-	-2,2706	[0.0116]**
1	-	-	-	-	-4,1063	[0.0000]***
2	-	-	-	-	-4,3026	[0.0000]***
3	-	-	-	-	-3,6470	[0.0001]***
4	-	-	-	-	-4,3934	[0.0000]***
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat						
0	-	-	-0,6155	0.2691	-2,7438	[0.0030]***
1	-	-	0.76235	0.7771	-1,2569	0.1044
2	-	-	1.48880	0.9317	-0,1016	0.4595
3	-	-	-6,2005	[0.0000]***	-3,0948	[0.0010]***
4	-	-	-3,7333	[0.0001]***	-1,7158	[0.0431]**
Im-Pesaran-Shin t -bar						
0	-	-	-1,6512	-	[-2.71403]***	-
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square						
0	40.3850	0.3653	34.6763	0.6239	61.5960	[0.0091]***
1	30.1359	0.8146	26.2765	0.9245	49.8591	[0.0943]*
2	21.5970	0.9851	19.9634	0.9929	37.3257	0.5005
3	42.8599	0.2706	124.475	[0.0000]***	64.3843	[0.0048]***
4	29.8534	0.8246	91.3763	[0.0000]***	43.4911	0.2490
Choi-ADF Z-stat						
0	-0,4948	0.3104	-0,6238	0,2664	-2,7726	[0.0028]***
1	0,9720	0.8345	0,8552	0.8038	-1,2774	0.1007
2	2.10231	0.9822	2,0900	0.9817	0,7718	0,7799
3	-0,1716	0.4319	-5,2331	[0.0000]***	-2,4580	[0.007]***
4	1.11142	0.8668	-2,2146	[0.0134]**	-0,5869	0.2786
Fisher-PP Chi-Square	39.3927	0.4074	49.5406	[0.0995]*	59.9175	[0.0132]**
Choi-PP Z-stat	-0,1195	0.4524	-1,7268	[0.0421]**	-2,4541	[0.0071]***
Ho: Stationarity (common unit root process)						
Hadri Z-stat	-	-	12.8874	[0.0000]***	7.96190	[0.0000]***
Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat	-	-	12.3916	[0.0000]***	6.45350	[0.0000]***

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality. LLC, Fisher-PP and Hadri: Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel. Critical t -bar values obtained from original Im, Pesaran e Shin (2003) paper. In Hadri test, high correlation leads to severe size distortion, leading to over-rejection of the null.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 8 – Panel Unit Root Tests: $\ln(d_{it}/rpi_t)$

Model	Restricted		Individual Intercept		Intercept and Trend	
	Automatic Lag Length Selection (AIC): 0 to 4					
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*	-5,09552	[0.0000]***	-2,38531	[0.0085]***	-8,49012	[0.0000]***
Breitung t -stat	-	-	-	-	-6,45523	[0.0000]***
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat	-	-	0.36816	0.6436	-6,08052	[0.0000]***
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square	66.6386	[0.0028]***	30.5928	0.7979	103.591	[0.0000]***
Choi-ADF Z-stat	-3,77041	[0.0001]***	0.54857	0.7084	-5,54669	[0.0000]***
Fixed Lags						
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*						
0	-4,6359	[0.0000]***	-4,2985	[0.0000]***	-9,2589	[0.0000]***
1	-5,4494	[0.0000]***	-2,9482	[0.0016]***	-5,6599	[0.0000]***
2	-4,9674	[0.0000]***	0.47473	0.6825	-3,6396	[0.0001]***
3	-6,6183	[0.0000]***	-0,2382	0.4059	-2,3163	[0.0103]**
4	-7,3675	[0.0000]***	-2,5701	[0.0051]***	-0,1053	0,4581
Breitung t -stat						
0	-	-	-	-	-7,0509	[0.0000]***
1	-	-	-	-	-3,8601	[0.0001]***
2	-	-	-	-	-1,3439	[0.0895]*
3	-	-	-	-	-0,3096	0,3784
4	-	-	-	-	-0,0551	0,4780
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat						
0	-	-	-1,6220	[0.0524]*	-6,4221	[0.0000]***
1	-	-	-0,0884	0.4648	-3,3213	[0.0004]***
2	-	-	2.30597	0,9894	-2,5171	[0.0059]***
3	-	-	2.12015	0,9830	-1,7215	[0.0426]**
4	-	-	0,0491	0.5196	-1,3821	[0.0835]*
Im-Pesaran-Shin t -bar						
0	-	-	[-1.86316]***	-	[-3.44628]***	-
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square						
0	69,8298	[0.0013]***	46.2368	0,1687	109.271	[0.0000]***
1	71,0728	[0.0009]***	34.8069	0.6179	68,6632	[0.0017]***
2	56.6501	[0.0263]**	14.7155	0.9998	62.0666	[0.0082]***
3	77,3693	[0.0002]***	12,6275	1.0000	50,2907	[0.0875]*
4	90,6491	[0.0000]***	28,5764	0.8660	37.6216	0.4868
Choi-ADF Z-stat						
0	-4,0962	[0.0000]***	-1.6870	[0.0458]**	-5,6883	[0.0000]***
1	-4,1503	[0.0000]***	-0,0895	0,4644	-3,5115	[0.0002]***
2	-2,9852	[0.0014]***	3.00612	0,9987	-1,8493	[0.0322]**
3	-3,8173	[0.0001]***	3,0873	0,9990	-1,1098	0,1335
4	-5,2002	[0.0000]***	1.16681	0,8784	-0,2229	0,4118
Fisher-PP Chi-Square	71.1481	[0.0009]***	42.0507	0.2998	128.727	[0.0000]***
Choi-PP Z-stat	-4,1547	[0.0000]***	-1,0112	0.1560	-6,0296	[0.0000]***
Ho: Stationarity (common unit root process)						
Hadri Z-stat	-	-	10.0588	[0.0000]***	6.08075	[0.0000]***
Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat	-	-	10.3840	[0.0000]***	6.58750	[0.0000]***

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality. LLC, Fisher-PP and Hadri: Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel. Critical t -bar values obtained from original Im, Pesaran e Shin (2003) paper. In Hadri test, high correlation leads to severe size distortion, leading to over-rejection of the null.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 9 – Panel Unit Root Tests: $\ln(p_{it}/d_{it})$

Model	Restricted		Individual Intercept		Intercept and Trend	
	Automatic Lag Length Selection (AIC): 0 to 4					
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*	0,9207	0.8214	-7,4314	[0.0000]***	-9,8575	[0.0000]***
Breitung t -stat	-	-	-	-	-4,0628	[0.0000]***
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat	-	-	-5,6561	[0.0000]***	-7,2686	[0.0000]***
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square	16.4246	0.9991	98.8030	[0.0000]***	118.509	[0.0000]***
Choi-ADF Z-stat	2.31517	0.9897	-5,5439	[0.0000]***	-6,8077	[0.0000]***
Fixed Lags						
Method	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.	Stat.	Prob.
Ho: Unit Root (common unit root process)						
Levin-Lin-Chu t^*						
0	-0,6768	0.2493	-7,5096	[0.0000]***	-8,7274	[0.0000]***
1	0,0897	0.5357	-3,7880	[0.0001]***	-5,9819	[0.0000]***
2	2,3266	0.9900	-4,6717	[0.0000]***	-3,8049	[0.0001]***
3	2.25206	0.9878	-7,7817	[0.0000]***	-6,8276	[0.0000]***
4	2.04021	0.9793	-1,3151	[0.0942]*	-0,5330	0.2970
Breitung t -stat						
0	-	-	-	-	-3,9018	[0.0000]***
1	-	-	-	-	-4,1904	[0.0000]***
2	-	-	-	-	-3,1874	[0.0007]***
3	-	-	-	-	-2,0977	[0.0180]**
4	-	-	-	-	-2,3300	[0.0099]***
Ho: Unit Root (individual unit root process)						
Im-Pesaran-Shin W -stat						
0	-	-	-5,6798	[0.0000]***	-5,5960	[0.0000]***
1	-	-	-2,2525	[0.0121]**	-3,3798	[0.0004]***
2	-	-	-2,8588	[0.0021]***	-2,2744	[0.0115]**
3	-	-	-4,9641	[0.0000]***	-4,6352	[0.0000]***
4	-	-	-1,5202	[0.0642]*	-2,5130	[0.0060]***
Im-Pesaran-Shin t -bar						
0	-	-	[-2.7177]***	-	[-3.28183]***	-
Fisher-ADF Chi-Square						
0	23.4241	0.9694	98.2319	[0.0000]***	92,5410	[0.0000]***
1	16.9649	0.9987	54,0128	[0.0444]**	69.4866	[0.0014]***
2	10,8752	1,0000	60.5261	[0.0115]**	52.2975	[0.0612]*
3	11,2678	1,0000	90,0918	[0.0000]***	80.9519	[0.0001]***
4	13.1011	0.9999	44,1307	0,2284	48,6339	0.1157
Choi-ADF Z-stat						
0	0,7801	0.7823	-5,5898	[0.0000]***	-5,4040	[0.0000]***
1	1.77628	0.9622	-2,3896	[0.0084]***	-3,5429	[0.0002]***
2	3,5401	0.9998	-2,6051	[0.0046]***	-1,7646	[0.0388]**
3	3,6267	0.9999	-4,8542	[0.0000]***	-4,4830	[0.0000]***
4	3.30058	0.9995	-0,7539	0.2255	-1,6519	[0.0493]**
Fisher-PP Chi-Square	16.6648	0.9990	102.158	[0.0000]***	87.7192	[0.0000]***
Choi-PP Z-stat	2.25669	0.9880	-5,6978	[0.0000]***	-4,8319	[0.0000]***
Ho: Stationarity (common unit root process)						
Hadri Z-stat	-	-	8.94344	[0.0000]***	4.90039	[0.0000]***
Heterocedastic Consistent Z-stat	-	-	8.17192	[0.0000]***	4.67303	[0.0000]***

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality. LLC, Fisher-PP and Hadri: Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel. Critical t -bar values obtained from original Im, Pesaran e Shin (2003) paper. In Hadri test, high correlation leads to severe size distortion, leading to over-rejection of the null. Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 10 – Residual-Based Kao Tests: $\ln(d_{it}/rpi_t)$ and $\ln(p_{it}/rpi_t)$

Ho: No Cointegration									
Model with Individual Intercept									
Automatic Selection: 2 Lags based on AIC									
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))	D(RESID(-5))
<i>t</i>	-0.578378	0.547553	0.240670	-8.2723	0.2567	1.9307	2.7037	2.4586	1.7572
Prob.	0.2815	-	-	[0.0000]***	0.7976	[0.0545]*	[0.0073]***	[0.0145]**	[0.0799]*
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0.6987	0.0200	0.1344	0.1729	0.1387	0.0821
Std. Error	-	-	-	0.0845	0.0779	0.0696	0.0640	0.0564	0.0467
	R-squared	0.359367		Adjusted R-squared	0.348618		DW stat	1.855529	
Fixed Lag: 1									
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))	D(RESID(-5))
<i>t</i>	-2.67432	0.547553	0.240670	-10.2632	-1.1026	-	-	-	-
Prob.	[0.0037]***	-	-	[0.0000]***	0.2709	-	-	-	-
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0.5871	-0.0555	-	-	-	-
Std. Error	-	-	-	0.0572	0.0503	-	-	-	-
	R-squared	0.314529		Adjusted R-squared	0.312716		DW stat	1.989273	
Fixed Lag: 2									
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))	D(RESID(-5))
<i>t</i>	-1.008305	0.547553	0.240670	-8.68069	-0.722653	-0.548263	-	-	-
Prob.	0.1567	-	-	[0.0000]***	0.4704	0.5839	-	-	-
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0.578228	-0.045029	-0.028165	-	-	-
Std. Error	-	-	-	0.0666	0.0623	0.0514	-	-	-
	R-squared	0.306226		Adjusted R-squared	0.30235		DW stat	2.00231	
Fixed Lag: 3									
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))	D(RESID(-5))
<i>t</i>	-1.009833	0.547553	0.240670	-8.682141	0.181872	0.992354	1.748719	-	-
Prob.	0.1563	-	-	[0.0000]***	0.8558	0.3217	[0.0812]*	-	-
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0.642049	0.012756	0.061606	0.089116	-	-
Std. Error	-	-	-	0.074	0.0701	0.0621	0.051	-	-
	R-squared	0.324138		Adjusted R-squared	0.318139		DW stat	1.900052	
Fixed Lag: 4									
	ADF	Residual Variance	HAC Variance	RESID(-1)	D(RESID(-1))	D(RESID(-2))	D(RESID(-3))	D(RESID(-4))	D(RESID(-5))
<i>t</i>	-0.645677	0.547553	0.240670	-8.3362	0.2974	1.7297	2.1715	2.4325	-
Prob.	0.2592	-	-	[0.0000]***	0.7663	[0.0846]*	[0.0306]**	[0.0155]**	-
Coeff.	-	-	-	-0.6526	0.0215	0.1146	0.1271	0.1167	-
Std. Error	-	-	-	0.0783	0.0724	0.0662	0.0585	0.0480	-
	R-squared	0.336621		Adjusted R-squared	0.328277		DW stat	2.012181	

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 11 – Pedroni Multiple Tests: $\ln(d_{it}/rpi_t)$ e $\ln(p_{it}/rpi_t)$

Ho: No Cointegration							
Panel Tests				Group Tests			
v-Statistic T1	rho-Statistic T2	PP-statistic T3	ADF-statistic T4	rho-Statistic T5	PP-Statistic T6	ADF-Statistic T7	
Ha: Common AR coefficients (<i>within-dimension</i>)				Ha: Individual AR coefficients (<i>between-dimension</i>)			
Automatic Lag Length Selection: Max Lag of 4 based on AIC							
Restricted Model							
S1	-2,320615	0,852759	-0,327815	-0,450724	2,892510	-0,031545	0,190499
Prob.	[0,0270]**	0,2773	0,3781	0,3640	[0,0061]***	0,3987	0,3918
S2	-2,749949	1,405288	0,283771	0,151808	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0091]***	0,1486	0,3832	0,3944	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	0,725685	-7,502796	-8,381973	-8,177851	-4,679801	-8,272106	-7,118092
Prob.	0,3066	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***
S2	-0,565953	-7,008678	-8,045238	-7,906151	-	-	-
Prob.	0,3399	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-2,605238	-3,859219	-8,350767	-8,545791	-1,87901	-8,600209	-9,226538
Prob.	[0,0134]**	[0,0002]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0683]*	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***
S2	-3,78896	-4,272121	-9,451235	-10,24465	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0003]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	-	-	-
Fixed Lag: 1							
Restricted Model							
S1	-2,320615	0,852759	-0,327815	-0,736761	2,892510	-0,031545	-0,30462
Prob.	[0,0270]**	0,2773	0,3781	0,3041	[0,0061]***	0,3987	0,3809
S2	-2,749949	1,405288	0,283771	-0,449634	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0091]***	0,1486	0,3832	0,3606	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	0,725685	-7,502796	-8,381973	-4,663635	-4,679801	-8,272106	-5,102836
Prob.	0,3066	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***
S2	-0,565953	-7,008678	-8,045238	-5,445578	-	-	-
Prob.	0,3399	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-2,605238	-3,859219	-8,350767	-5,365327	-1,87901	-8,600209	-5,766578
Prob.	[0,0134]**	[0,0002]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0683]*	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***
S2	-3,78896	-4,272121	-9,451235	-7,115894	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0003]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	-	-	-
Lag Fixo: 2							
Restricted Model							
S1	-2,320615	0,852759	-0,327815	0,565074	2,892510	-0,031545	1,193997
Prob.	[0,0270]**	0,2773	0,3781	0,3401	[0,0061]***	0,3987	0,1956
S2	-2,749949	1,405288	0,283771	0,797833	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0091]***	0,1486	0,3832	0,2902	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	0,725685	-7,502796	-8,381973	-2,718612	-4,679801	-8,272106	-2,50548
Prob.	0,3066	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0099]**	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0173]**
S2	-0,565953	-7,008678	-8,045238	-2,25192	-	-	-
Prob.	0,3399	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0316]**	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-2,605238	-3,859219	-8,350767	-3,861804	-1,87901	-8,600209	-3,082535
Prob.	[0,0134]**	[0,0002]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0002]***	[0,0683]*	[0,0000]***	[0,0034]***
S2	-3,78896	-4,272121	-9,451235	-3,646666	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0003]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0005]***	-	-	-
Lag Fixo: 3							
Restricted Model							
S1	-2,320615	0,852759	-0,327815	0,379225	2,892510	-0,031545	-0,210801
Prob.	[0,0270]**	0,2773	0,3781	0,3713	[0,0061]***	0,3987	0,3902
S2	-2,749949	1,405288	0,283771	0,476399	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0091]***	0,1486	0,3832	0,3561	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	0,725685	-7,502796	-8,381973	-2,826191	-4,679801	-8,272106	-1,843368
Prob.	0,3066	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0074]**	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0730]*
S2	-0,565953	-7,008678	-8,045238	-2,099366	-	-	-
Prob.	0,3399	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0440]**	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-2,605238	-3,859219	-8,350767	-2,589613	-1,87901	-8,600209	-1,9807
Prob.	[0,0134]**	[0,0002]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0140]**	[0,0683]*	[0,0000]***	[0,0561]*
S2	-3,78896	-4,272121	-9,451235	-2,081384	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0003]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0457]**	-	-	-
Lag Fixo: 4							
Restricted Model							
S1	-2,320615	0,852759	-0,327815	-0,428197	2,892510	-0,031545	-1,453913
Prob.	[0,0270]**	0,2773	0,3781	0,3640	[0,0061]***	0,3987	0,1386
S2	-2,749949	1,405288	0,283771	-0,216119	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0091]***	0,1486	0,3832	0,3897	-	-	-
Model with Individual Intercept							
S1	0,725685	-7,502796	-8,381973	-2,040289	-4,679801	-8,272106	-0,73111
Prob.	0,3066	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0048]**	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	0,3054
S2	-0,565953	-7,008678	-8,045238	-1,217195	-	-	-
Prob.	0,3399	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	0,1902	-	-	-
Model with Intercept and Trend							
S1	-2,605238	-3,859219	-8,350767	-2,553367	-1,87901	-8,600209	-1,687606
Prob.	[0,0134]**	[0,0002]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0153]**	[0,0683]*	[0,0000]***	[0,0960]*
S2	-3,78896	-4,272121	-9,451235	-1,790198	-	-	-
Prob.	[0,0003]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0000]***	[0,0804]*	-	-	-

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. S1 represents the statistics, and S2 denotes the weighted statistics. Newey-West bandwidth selection using Bartlett kernel.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

Table 12 – Panel Johansen-Fisher Test: $\ln(d_{it}/rpi_t)$ e $\ln(p_{it}/rpi_t)$

Deterministic Trend Specification: No Trend in Data				
No Intercept or trend in CE or VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	46.52	0.1616	50.43	[0.0855]*
At most 1	18.35	0.9970	18.35	0.9970
Intercept (no trend) in CE - no intercept in VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(a partir do <i>trace test</i>)		(a partir do <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	65.09	[0.0040]***	47.60	0.1367
At most 1	52.18	[0.0626]*	52.18	[0.0626]*
Deterministic Trend Specification: Linear Trend in Data				
Intercept (no trend) in CE and VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	69.49	[0.0014]***	55.82	[0.0311]***
At most 1	69.45	[0.0014]***	69.45	[0.0014]***
Intercept and trend in CE - no trend in VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	58.79	[0.0168]*	53.60	[0.0479]**
At most 1	33.30	0.6864	33.30	0.6864
Deterministic Trend Specification: Quadratic Trend in Data				
Intercept and trend in CE - linear trend in VAR				
Hypothesized	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.	Fisher Stat.*	Prob.
No. of CE(s)	(from <i>trace test</i>)		(from <i>max-eigen test</i>)	
None	116.2	[0.0000]***	71.08	[0.0009]***
At most 1	138.4	[0.0000]***	138.4	[0.0000]***

Note: ***, **, * represent test statistics significant to the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Lags interval (in first differences): 1 1. Probabilities are computed using asymptotic χ^2 distribution.

Source: Elaborated by the authors.

